

PSYCHOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF READING ON HUMAN CONSCIOUSNESS

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Abstract: *The article is proves that reading has impacts. The reading increases the thinking ability of the person and promotes memory effectively. Reading enhances brain connectivity and function. Stories impact the brain both psychologically and neurologically.*

Keywords: *self-learning, effects of reading, literate, book, literature, consciousness, impact.*

It is impossible to imagine building a society without scientific knowledge. Everything depends on human knowledge, spiritual maturity, and spirituality to reading.

Reading has great impact on human beings. The book serves as a fundamental human bridge to study diverse cultures and knowledge. Reading is a source of vocabulary that can be used to enrich your vocabulary. The more a person reads, the more fluent, the more literate, the more literate he will be. Worldwide, the cultural level is growing.

As human beings read too much, their knowledge grows, they become aware of everything in the field, and as a result, they become an interesting chatterer, rightly speaking counselor.

At present, self-learning is a necessity of life, and it is quite possible that no one is left behind the caravan. Readers also need to know certain terms for use by any means of communication.

The First President of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov said:

"Our youth should be a reader. It is possible to achieve high progress only when there is a true readability".

Goethe writes about the book readings:

a) is extremely difficult (indeed, the book's reading requires hard and persistent memory, strong memory, and high level of understanding);

b) An exceptional honor (due to the text of the book, deep understanding of the laws of life, the expansion of the sphere of knowledge, the understanding, the outlook, the spiritual rise);

c) the rest (otherwise it would not have been busy with the book study).

A study was conducted at Sussex University to investigate stress relief methods. And it has been proven that no media can help. Scientists have said that the reading process can reduce stress levels up to 68 percent. It is enough for the muscles to relax and hit the pulse rate for six minutes. The study found that music playback decreased stress by 61 percent, tea or coffee - by 54 percent, and walking - by 42 percent.

The reading increases the thinking ability of the person and promotes memory effectively. American scientists have tested that 294 people under the age of 89 tested loneliness and found that mental health was 15 percent higher than others and 32 percent higher in adolescents who spend 2-3 hours each day reading books.

Every time the book is read, brain activates. Because the brain creates new fibers to store the information they receive.

Scientists at the Ohio State University say that the more books a human being reads, the more accurate the choice of life is.

When Obafemi attends the classroom comic book on Avolau University's teachers, a mix of pictures and lyrics has revealed that children's creative abilities develop.

Psychological effects of reading:

Nerves the nerves;

Helps relieve insomnia;

- Improves brain activity;
- Stimulates morale;
- helps to understand the purpose of life and overcome difficulties;
- Increasing vocabulary;
- Developing creativity;
- Facilitates learning foreign languages;
- Developing listening skills;
- Reading books together improves the relationship between

parent and child;

- helps to master the lesson;
- Makes good conduct;
- Teaches others to understand;
- It corrects mistakes.

Also, the study of readers has shown that those who are busy with more studies are physically healthy, tidy, cheerful, spiritually balanced and healthy, and have a higher position than others.

The purpose of the wide-ranging spiritual and educational reforms in our country is to raise the literacy culture, to bring up the educated and

spiritually-minded youth - the comprehensively advanced generation, who have the vision and outlook, the active civic position.

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